

Fully-connected Committee Machine (FCM) based Online Learning under Concept Drift

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Abstract

The term “drift” refers to unanticipated changes in the transmission of data in the primary distribution over time. Conceptual drift research entails developing methods and strategies for detecting, interpreting, and adapting to drift. Machine learning approaches can produce poor learning outcomes in the conceptual drift environment if drift is not addressed. Furthermore, due to developments in the concept of drift, revealing a method not mentioned in the literature, the concept of drift learning methodologies has been significantly systematic in recent years. We used a layered neural network framework to experiment with different scenarios of online learning under concept drift using a fully-connected committee machine (FCM). We conduct experiments in various scenarios using a layered neural network framework for online learning under concept drift. In neural layered networks, sigmoidal and ReLU activation functions are considered for learning regression. When the layered framework is trained from the input dynamic data stream, the regression scheme changes consciously in all scenarios. A fully-connected committee machine (FCM) is trained to perform the tasks described in online learning with M hidden units on dynamically generated inputs. In this method, we run Monte Carlo simulations with the same number of units on both sides, K and M , to define the dynamic advancement of intersections between several hidden units and the calculation of generalization error. This is applied to over-learnability as a method of over-forgetting, integrating weight decay, and examining its effects in the presence of concept drift.

Keywords: Online Learning, Fully-connected Committee Machine (FCM), Concept Drift, Dynamic data streams.

1. Introduction

Contemporary hypothetical studies show that the generalization and representation power of neural networks will increase as the depth of neural networks increases [2, 22]. But, dynamic data stream analysis remains unexplored in neural network environments.

The direct use of traditional neural network models for streaming data analysis is often not possible due to their high computing and memory requirements so that they cannot be implemented with limited computing resources [10]. Dynamic data streams should preferably be sampled without retraining to avoid the catastrophic problem of forgetting and to adapt to the nature of the learning environment [10, 8]. In dynamic environments, these characteristics with changing dynamic data streaming properties do not reflect effectively. This is a new challenge for conventional neural networks with fixed and static structures [7]. To address these issues, the capacity of the neural network must likely be estimated before the adaptation of continuous learning using concept drift.

Feed-forward neural networks are widely used tools for classification and regression. Shallow networks of only one hidden layer are already sufficient to denote the non-trivial scalar function of N-dimensional variables [15]. However, the convergence of the training of such networks may be very slow due to the occurrence of the so-called plateau states. As far as online learning in a scenario is concerned, students can get stuck in an unspecialized local optimum before they quickly specialize in the hidden teacher unit.

In this paper, we consider two options for activation functions in hidden units. Conventionally, sigmoid activation functions have been used, but recently, ReLU activation has gained popularity, mostly due to improved empirical performance. Theoretical advantages have also been demonstrated in [16].

Generally, a machine learning approach is carried out with the training phase and later with the testing phase [23]. During the training phase, data instances are presented, analyzed, extracted information, and the classifier hypothesis or regression scheme is parameterized. This hypothesis can be tested with new data at the next stage of the testing phase. This process implicitly assumes that the training set does not change, that the statistical properties of the data and the actual target class remain the same after training. However, this is not always the case in machine learning tasks and is not a plausible assumption as to how learning happens in humans and other biological processes. In such circumstances, the learning system must be able to identify and monitor the concept of drift, i.e. to forget irrelevant, old information while constantly adjusting to more recent inputs. This process is also known as online learning under concept drift. The theoretical properties and statistical mechanics of concept drift have been studied before [17, 18]. In this paper, the focus lies on practical simulations of scenarios to learn a regression scheme in varying situations.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the basic preliminaries and related work associate with concept drift. Section 3 presents the research methodology for online learning under concept drift. Section 4 discusses evaluation systems. Section 5 elaborates widespread empirical investigations of key discoveries and presents further research aspects associated with online learning.

2. Basic Preliminaries and Related Research Work

This section defines the basic preliminaries and related research work associated with Concept drift in online learning.

2.1 Concept Drift

Concept Drift is an occurrence in which the statistical properties of a data change randomly occurred with time [11]. It was proposed with the intention that the noise data can be converted into noise-free at different times [21], [9], [24], and [12]. These deviations may be due to hidden properties in the variables which cannot be measured directly [1]. Formally, the drift of the concept in learning is defined:

In a time interval ranging from $[0...t]$, a set of data examples denoted as $D_{0,t} = \{D_0...D_t\}$, where $D_i = (X_i, Y_i)$ is a data instance, representing where X_i is the feature vector, Y_i is the class label, and $D_{0,t}$ follows a certain probability distribution $P_{0,t}(X; y)$. Concept drift occurs at timestamp $t+1$, if the condition $P_{0,t}(X, y) \neq P_{t+1,t}(X, y)$. The drift or change in concept is just a subcategory of the change in the data set consists of the change in covariates and the previous change in probability and change in concept. These definitions have set out the scope of research for each research topic.

2.2. Online Learning

Online learning of evolving dynamic data streams is defined as a learning approach of continuously generated data batches $B \in \{B_1, \dots, B_k, \dots, B_K\}$ where the number of data batches K and the type of data distributions are unknown before the process runs. B_k can be either a single data point or a particular size of data batch. Data points enter the scene with the lack of a valid class marker for data flow problems [10]. Access to the reality or work experience of the subject depends on the implementation of the labeling process. In other words, if the true class designations $C \in R^T$ are revealed, a delay is predicted. To obtain $C \in R^{T \times m}$, the 0-1 coding scheme can be implemented. This problem limits the feasibility of training as a cross-validation evaluation protocol since these approaches assume that the entire sample batches are completely measurable and there is a possibility that the time order of the data will be lost [10, 3].

The Neural network to handle B_k has to process dynamic data streams for the dynamic data streams that can originate from several data distributions, which are often referred to as drift term. In particular, the setback probability for the common class $P(C_t, X_t) \neq P(C_{t-1}, X_{t-1})$ can change. The concept of drift is usually seen in the real and the covariate [16]. This also means that the model developed using the previous definition of B_{k-1} is out of date. This feature has some relevance to the multitasking learning issue, where separate tasks come from each batch of B_k results. However, Neural Networks differ from multitasking methods in that a single paradigm is to process all data batches instead of focusing on specific task classifiers. The compromise will increase the likelihood of over-forgetting; there is another problem with data flows [6]. Such specifications require an online Neural Network architecture that is capable of constantly rebuilding its

network structure from scratch concerning the provision of dynamic data streams. To avoid catastrophic oblivion, a mechanism must also be put in place to repeat the previous experience and to keep it flexible or to acquire a new one.

In the following sections, we present a scenario for a regression scheme [19] with neural networks with low feedback. Two types of hidden activation units, sigmoid and the ReLU, are explained and compared. In this paper, the gradient-based training of a fully-connected committee machine is regarded as an explicit forgetting process in the presence of a real drift term, like weight loss.

3. Online Learning using Fully-Connected Committee Machine

In the following sections, we present continuous learning based on a between the regression regime [19] and the shallow forward neural networks. We're explaining and comparing two types of hidden activation units, *Sigmoidal* and *ReLU*. To study the effect of continuous learning, we have considered gradient-based training of a fully-connected Committee Machine (FCM) in the existence of a real concept of drift with the inclusion of weight decay as a mechanism of explicit oblivion.

3.1. Fully-connected Committee Machines

A fully-connected committee machine (FCM) is a forward neural network architecture that contains a single hidden layer and single linear output unit with a non-linear activation function. It is possible to characterize the output of an FCM as

$$y(\xi) = \sum_{k=1}^K g(W_k \cdot \xi) \quad (1)$$

Here, W_k denotes the weight vector that connects this input data with the K^{th} hidden unit. A nonlinear activation $g(x)$ outlines the sum as the states of the hidden units and the final output.

For the Sigmoidal case, this corresponds

$$g(x) = \text{erf}(x/\sqrt{2}), \quad g'(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \cdot e^{-x^2/2} \quad (2)$$

For the ReLU case, this corresponds

$$g(x) = x \theta(x), \quad g'(x) = \theta(x) \quad (3)$$

$$\theta(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where $\theta(x)$ is the step function, defined as

Figure 1: (a) Sigmoidal activation using the erf(x) function, (b) ReLU activation: $x\theta(x)$

Both activation functions have their advantages and disadvantages [20] and their characteristics with the inclusion of drift can vary. In Figure 1 we can see the plots of the activation functions. We observe that the derivative of the erf function is Gaussian in nature, while the ReLU derivative is 0 for $x < 0$ and 1 for $x > 0$ [20]. One property to account for is the discontinuity of $\text{ReLU}(0)$, in practice, one can choose either 0 or 1 in this situation.

3.2 Online Learning

In general, the training of a forward neural network with output values $y(\xi)$ is driven by the squared deviation of the output of the network from the output of the rule, according to the examples $\mu \in \mathbb{R}^N$, $\mu \in \mathbb{C}$ or $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$. This variance is a cost function that assesses the efficiency of the network:

$$\{x^\mu \in \mathbb{R}^N, T^\mu \in \mathbb{R}\} \tag{4}$$

In gradient descent, the weight vectors are updated based on a single example at time step μ is given as

$$e^\mu \left(\{W_k\}_{k=1}^K \right) = \frac{1}{2} (y^\mu - T^\mu)^2 \quad \text{with } y^\mu = y(\xi^\mu) \tag{5}$$

$$\Delta W_K^\mu = - \left(\sum_{i=1}^K g(h_i^\mu) - T^\mu \right) g'(h_K^\mu) \xi^\mu \tag{6}$$

The next instance in the input data stream is estimated as the function of inner products $h^\mu = \mathbf{w}^{\mu-1} \cdot \xi^\mu$ of the current weight vectors. This transformation of weight vectors is proportional to ξ^μ and inferred Hebbian learning [23].

3.3 The Learning Scenario

We made use of learning scenarios to classify and model meaningful learning scenarios. The goal is well-defined as FCM with M hidden units with associated weight vector, we assume $\{\mathbf{B}_m \in \mathbb{R}^N\}_{m=1}^M$

$$T(\xi) = \sum_{m=1}^M g(\mathbf{B}_m \cdot \xi) \text{ and } T^\mu = T(\xi^\mu) \tag{7}$$

with $b^\mu = \mathbf{B}_m \cdot \xi$. There are three different scenarios with regards to hidden units. $M > K$ hidden units as unlearnable. On the contrary, $K > M$ would correspond to an overlearnable, also known as overfitting. In practice, one usually does not know the complexity of the task, making this an interesting case to study. The last and most studied scenario has $K = M$, where the two architectures match and has to ability to fully represent the rule, without any redundancies. In this paper, the focus lies on scenarios with $K = M$.

3.4. Order Parameters

It is possible to describe quantities in the different components of adaptive vectors. The description of these order parameters follows the statistical model of adaptive quantities. The order parameters quantify the similarity of student weight vectors with other student weight vectors and the similarity between student and teacher weight vectors. The number μ of examples, the order parameters are presented as

$$R_{im} = \mathbf{w}_i \cdot \mathbf{B}_m, Q_{ik} = \mathbf{w}_i \cdot \mathbf{w}_k \quad m = 1 \dots M \quad I, k = 1 \dots K.$$

3.5. Generalization Error

The learning success is quantified after the training based on the generalization error so-called, which is also given depending on the order parameters. The generalization error can be defined as the mean value of the quadratic divergence over the isotropic density between the outputs [17]. For the sigmoidal case, this equates to

$$\epsilon_g = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[\sum_{i,j=1}^K \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{Q_{ij}}{\sqrt{1+Q_{ii}}\sqrt{1+Q_{jj}}} \right) - 2 \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{m=1}^M \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{R_{im}}{\sqrt{1+Q_{ii}}\sqrt{2}} \right) \right] + \frac{M}{6} \tag{8}$$

For the ReLU case,

$$\epsilon_g = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{i,j=1}^K \left(\frac{Q_{ij}}{4} + \frac{\sqrt{Q_{ii}Q_{jj} - Q_{ij}^2}}{2\pi} + \frac{Q_{ij} \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{Q_{ij}}{\sqrt{Q_{ii}Q_{jj}}} \right)}{2\pi} \right) - 2 \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{m=1}^M \left(\frac{R_{im}}{4} + \frac{\sqrt{Q_{ii} - R_{im}^2}}{2\pi} + \frac{R_{im} \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{R_{im}}{\sqrt{Q_{ii}}} \right)}{2\pi} \right) + \frac{M}{2} + \frac{(M-1)M}{2\pi} \right] \tag{9}$$

Both equations are for orthonormal teacher vectors, where $\mathbf{B}_m \cdot \mathbf{B}_m = 1$ and $\mathbf{B}_m \cdot \mathbf{B}_n = 0$ for $m, n = 1 \dots M$. Extensions to general teacher vectors exist [23].

3.6. Concept Drift

The models, as explained in the previous sections, online learning in a stationary network, where the characteristic vectors $\mathbf{B}_m$ do not change during the training. We would like to extend this to non-stationary environments, which are divided into two categories, virtual drift, and real drift. Virtual drift affects the statistical properties of the observed instances of the data, while the actual target function remains unchanged. In this paper, we focus on the other category, *real drift*. Here, the actual target changes, i.e. the characteristic vectors $\mathbf{B}_m$ displaces over time. Important to note is that, in practice, real drift progressions are often conveyed by virtual drift [4]. We restrict ourselves to the analysis of real concept drift under random displacements of vectors $\mathbf{B}_m(\mu)$ at each time step. The random vectors B_m are generated using the following two conditions

$$\mathbf{B}_M(\mu) \cdot \mathbf{B}_M(\mu - 1) = (1 - f/N) \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_M(\mu) \cdot \mathbf{B}_M(\mu - 1) = 0 \text{ for } M \neq N \quad (11)$$

With $m, n = 1 \dots M$. Here δ enumerates the drift process strength.

3.7. Weight Decay

We embrace a weight decay to implement exclusive forgetting and to possibly increase the system performance in the presence of concept drift. To evaluate the system, before the generic learning step, we have considered the product of adaptive vectors by a factor $(1, \gamma/N)$ as:

$$W_i^\mu = (1 - r/N)W_i^{\mu-1} + n/N \Delta W_i^\mu \quad (12)$$

The product with $(1, \gamma/N)$ gathered in the training, thereby enforcing an improved effect of the previous training data as associated with previous instances.

3.8. Learning Framework

For this learning, a framework has been developed in which we can run Monte Carlo simulations. Random input vectors $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$ are generated using the weights with preset overlap. Here we use

$$R_{im} = 0, \quad Q_{1i} = 0.5, \quad Q_{ik} = 0.49, \text{ for } I \neq k, \quad (13)$$

where $i, k = 1 \dots K$ and $m = 1 \dots M$. This means that the students have no prior knowledge of the rule and a large amount of overlap between themselves, resulting in longer plateau states. We use a generalized version of the Gram-Schmidt method to initialize the overlap. Different parameters can be tweaked to compare different initializations, the drift strength δ , the learning rate, γ , and the number of student vectors and hidden teacher units. Furthermore, the total amount of time steps μ can be adapted. The resulting graphs generally have $\alpha = \mu/N$ along the x-axis, this scale is based on the assumption that the

number of examples required for successful training is proportional to the number of degrees of freedom in the system.

4 Performance Evaluation and Analysis

Here we present the results obtained from the Monte Carlo simulations of Online learning with drift. We distinguish on the important scenarios, firstly, $K = M$, the exact case with an equal number of matching vectors and its relation with concept drift. In all of the following experiments, we use system size $N = 500$. The empirical study of Concept drifts based Online learning in which it is compared against four algorithms.

Firstly, we look at the matching case, where $K = M = 2$ and the two architectures match. In Figure 2 we can see the generalization error s_g over time for both sigmoidal and ReLU activation. The results are for simulations run with $\eta = 0.5$, $\alpha = 800$ for sigmoidal activation and $\alpha = 150$ for ReLU activation. These results are then averaged over 5 runs. We observe that, as the drift strength increases, the final generalization error also increases.

Figure 2: (a) Generalization error for sigmoidal activation, for different δ 's, (b) ReLU activation

4.1. Effects of Higher K

As the complexity of the rule is often unknown in practice, situations where $K > M$ can occur. Furthermore, with the inclusion of drift, it might even serve more useful to have an overlearnable target. In Figure 3 we can see the final generalization error as a function of K . In this simulation, we use a smaller learning rate, $\eta = 0.1$. We use $\alpha = 1200$ for sigmoidal activation and $\alpha = 500$ for ReLU.

Figure 3: (a) Final generalization error versus K for sigmoidal, (b) ReLU

4.2. Optimal Learning Rate

Figure 4 shows the optimal learning rate as a function of the generalization error, for 2 situations. In the first one, $K = M = 2$, and in the second one, $K > M$, with $K = 4$ and $M = 2$. In both cases, $\alpha = 800$ for sigmoidal and $\alpha = 300$ for ReLU. The final generalization error is averaged of the last 75000 time-steps in which the students have achieved optimal overlap with the teachers.

Figure 4: (a) Generalization error versus learning rate, for different δ s. Sigmoidal activation $K = M = 2$, (b) Sigmoidal activation, $K = 4$, $M = 2$, (c) ReLU activation, $K = M = 2$, (d) ReLU activation, $K = 4$, $M = 2$.

4.3. Effect of Weight Decay

Figure 5 shows the effect of weight decay on the final generalization error for both ReLU and sigmoidal activation. Here, $K = 2$, $M = 2$, $\eta = 0.5$, $\alpha = 800$ for sigmoidal and $\alpha = 300$ for ReLU. The final generalization error is again averaged of the last 75000 time steps in which the students have achieved optimal overlap with the teachers.

4.4. Discussion

Starting with the $K = M$ situation, from Figure 2 we can observe that ReLU activation is better able to handle real drift. As with sigmoidal activation, for $\delta > 0.03$, the FCM remains unspecialized and the achievable generalization ability is quite poor. In the ReLU case, for higher δ 's, it might look like the same is happening. However, after a rapid decrease, a short plateau is reached and this symmetry is quickly broken before the system reaches its final generalized state.

As shown in Figure 3, it might serve useful to have an overlearnable target. In practice, one rarely knows the complexity of the rule. So when one suspects there is drift in the learning process, increasing K to improve generalization can be considered. A consequence of this is the increased risk of overfitting

In Figure 4, we can see that the optimal learning rate with significant drift is around 0.5, for both ReLU and sigmoidal. As the number of hidden units K increases, lower learning rates are more ideal. Furthermore, the threshold for divergence will decrease with increasing K , a learning rate that is too high will not facilitate any progress and the student weight vectors will diverge from the rule.

Figure 5: (a) Generalization error versus weight decay, ReLU, $\delta = 0.05$, (b) ReLU, $\delta = 0.3$ (c) Sigmoidal, $\delta = 0.005$, (d) Sigmoidal, $\delta = 0.03$

Looking at Figure 5, we can observe that larger amounts of drift benefit from a higher value of γ . As ReLU is generally more able to deal with larger drift, it also benefits more from a higher value of γ in those situations. This is logical, if a system is highly non-stationary, it has to be more able to forget old data. Since sigmoidal activation does not handle drifts of $\delta > 0.01$ desirably, weight decay has little to no effect. For low amounts of drift, any weight decay increases the final generalization error.

5. Conclusion

This paper focused mostly on the effect of real drift with regards to Online learning of a regression scheme using two different activation functions. Especially, the differences between the matching and overlearnable situations, and the possible advantages and disadvantages between them. The comparison of simulations with the theoretical description of the learning dynamics [17], where $N \rightarrow \infty$. The effect of weight decay and drift on the actual plateau lengths and the generalization error s_p in these plateau states. Deterministic concept drifts, similar to perceptron learning can *adversely* model a new system with the target configuration [13, 14, 5]. As deep learning [26] has been an interesting topic of research in recent years, the extension to a deeper FCM architecture, with more than one hidden layer is an important forthcoming study. A more practical approach can be researched, with realistic dynamic data streams, to infer whether the results in this learning can be observed in real-world situations.

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